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- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
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STRUCTURE OF SOCIAL CONFLICT AND STAGES OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

Zaynutdinova Shahnoza Yuldashevna
Independent researcher, TSUE

Annotatsiya: This article examines the process of conflict from its emergence to its transformation. Conflicts, much like living beings, are born, grow, evolve, and reach a certain level of maturity. However, the nature of conflict has an interesting and important feature: unlike living beings, conflicts do not simply die out or end over time. Instead, they transform. What, then, does a conflict transform into? To answer this question, it is first necessary to understand the stages of conflict development, how it manifests itself at each stage, and which type of intervention can be most effective, and when.

Kalit so'zlar: social conflict, conflictological approach, society, structure of social conflict, stages of conflict, phases, parties to a conflict, confrontation.

Abstract: This article examines the process of conflict from its emergence to its transformation. Conflicts, much like living beings, are born, grow, evolve, and reach a certain level of maturity. However, the nature of conflict has an interesting and important feature: unlike living beings, conflicts do not simply die out or end over time. Instead, they transform. What, then, does a conflict transform into? To answer this question, it is first necessary to understand the stages of conflict development, how it manifests itself at each stage, and which type of intervention can be most effective, and when.

Key words: social conflict, conflictological approach, society, structure of social conflict, stages of conflict, phases, parties to a conflict, confrontation.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается процесс конфликта – от его возникновения до трансформации. Конфликты, подобно живым организмам, рождаются, развиваются, эволюционируют и достигают определённого уровня зрелости. Однако природа конфликта имеет одну важную особенность: в отличие от живых существ, конфликты не исчезают и не прекращаются с течением времени. Напротив, они трансформируются. Возникает вопрос: во что же трансформируется конфликт? Чтобы ответить на этот вопрос, прежде всего необходимо знать стадии развития конфликта, его проявления на каждом этапе, а также определить, какое вмешательство и на каком этапе может быть наиболее эффективным.

Ключевые слова: социальный конфликт, конфликтологический подход, общество, структура социального конфликта, стадии конфликта, фазы, стороны конфликта, противостояние.

INTRODUCTION

The genesis of conflict theory stems from ancient philosophies. Plato and Aristotle believed that a person is part of a wider whole, that is, society; therefore, the social principle inherent in him implies mutual understanding and cooperation. At the same time, the tendency toward enmity, hatred, and violence was not excluded. According to Aristotle, this was due to the inequality of people, their vices, and the dissimilarity of characters. Ancient Chinese scholars were also concerned about the problem of conflicts. In philosophical treatises, Confucius argued that conflicts are caused by the inequality and dissimilarity of people, as well as their vices: stubbornness, flattery, deceit, greed, rhetoric, selfishness, etc.

The founders of sociology—Auguste Comte, Herbert Spencer, and others—made their contribution to the development of conflict theory. In the first half of the 19th century, the first attempts were made to justify the role of conflict in sociological theory, which was facilitated by the work of the English sociologist Herbert Spencer *Fundamentals of Sociology*. H. Spencer emphasized the universality of the phenomenon of conflict and regarded it as a normal social phenomenon. A scientific approach to the analysis of conflicts appeared only in the second half of the 19th century. At that time, conflicts were put forward in a number of subjects of special study. These ideas were accepted and developed by such representatives of the social sciences as Emile Durkheim, Max Weber, Georg Simmel, and Karl Marx.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the 20th century, the German researcher Ralf Dahrendorf and his American colleague Lewis Coser contributed to the study of social conflicts. For R. Dahrendorf, conflict is the natural state of society, while its absence is considered abnormal. L. Coser provided a deep justification for the positive role of conflict interaction in the life of society. One of the prominent sociologists developing the theory of social conflict was R. Dahrendorf (1929-2009), who considered conflict to be an integral part of social development, insofar as there have always been and will be relations of "domination-subordination" in society. These relations presuppose the presence of opposing views, judgments, principles, and norms of behavior among participants in this type of social interaction. R. Dahrendorf contrasted conflict with integration and considered it to be as inevitable as the integration of social institutions. Since it is not always possible to avoid conflict, he argued that it is necessary to formalize it, i.e., bring it to the surface of public life and make it the subject of open discussions or legal proceedings, which would contribute to maintaining the stability of the social system.

The role of social conflict in society was most fully disclosed by the American sociologist L. Coser (1913-2003) in his works *Functions of Social Conflicts* and *Continued Study of Social Conflict*, in which conflict is defined as an ideological phenomenon that manifests itself in the struggle for power, revaluation of values, etc. Conflict is a clash of interests and values, manifested in the ideological confrontation of interacting parties, which can develop into revolutionary violence, destroying social ties and the social system as a whole.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A social conflict is a clash of opposing goals, interests, positions, opinions, or views of the subjects of interaction. There are several points of view on conflict in social relations. The extreme positions are as follows. Conflict in social relations is always present in different forms. Conflict between individual elements of the social structure is considered a normal state of society. Only conflicts in the acute stage of development are dangerous. The task of the parties to the conflict is to understand the opposite side and bring their positions closer together by finding a compromise. This point of view is characteristic of the conflictological approach.

Another position is that conflict is dangerous for society. It must be extinguished by all possible methods, and a compromise must be reached at any cost. Compromise means an agreement between opposing positions, opinions, or directions, achieved through mutual concessions. After reaching a compromise, it is necessary to move from conflict to cooperation, where cooperation is understood as the mutually beneficial development of the process. This point of view can conditionally be designated as functional. Functions of conflict (according to L. Coser): establishment of clear boundaries of a specific group; centralization of decision-making in a group; integration of the group; soft conflicts prevent more severe ones; soft conflicts allow the entire social system to change more easily, replace obsolete norms, and create new necessary ones.

There are also a number of intermediate positions between these extremes. Based on different understandings of the role of conflict in society, the two approaches view the mutual influence of cooperation and conflict differently. From the conflictological perspective, cooperation arises directly from the structure of conflict: successful resolution of a conflict inevitably leads to cooperation in one form or another. From the functional perspective, cooperation does not follow from the conflict structure itself but arises only in the event of a successful resolution. Otherwise, the conflict may enter a latent (hidden) phase and subside without any cooperation between the parties.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The main signs of a conflict include the presence of a situation perceived by the opposing parties as conflictual, opposing goals, needs, interests, and methods of achieving them, interaction between the conflicting parties and the results of this interaction, as well as the use of pressure and force. The main causes of conflict are the distribution of resources, the interdependence of people and organizations, differences in goals and objectives, differences in ideas and values, and communicative differences in the methods and ways of mutual communication. Conflictology has developed two main models for describing conflict: the process model and the structural model. The process model focuses on the dynamics of conflict, the emergence of a conflict situation, the transition of the conflict from one phase to another, forms of conflict behavior, and the final outcome of the conflict, while the structural model emphasizes the analysis of the conditions underlying the conflict and determining its dynamics, with the main goal of establishing the parameters that influence conflict behavior and specifying the forms of this influence.

The stages of conflict can be characterized by time and intensity, since changes in the intensity of conflict can be observed as time passes. Every conflict usually begins in a latent or potential stage, when elements that could lead to conflict exist but are not yet visible, with communication gaps, misunderstandings, power

imbalances, or unsurfaced tensions being typical symptoms. As the conflict develops, differences of opinion and disagreements become more apparent, the parties adopt more defensive or aggressive attitudes, and tension increases in communication, marking the confrontation stage. When tension reaches its peak, serious disagreements arise, positions harden, and emotional reactions intensify, the conflict enters a crisis stage, often leading to a deadlock. Over time, however, efforts to resolve the conflict emerge, motivation to find solutions grows, and constructive dialogue takes shape, which defines the outcome stage. Finally, in the post-conflict stage, relationships between the parties are restructured, lessons are learned, strategies to prevent recurrence are developed, and efforts are made to rebuild trust; if resolution is positive, bonds are strengthened, but if not, the conflict may resurface in another form. It should be emphasized that the conflict cycle does not always follow this strict order, since early interventions can stop escalation before crisis, while superficial solutions may reignite disputes and return the process to confrontation or crisis again.

It is important to know these stages because, in order to be able to use the proper methods of intervention in conflicts, it is necessary to know at what time and with what intensity the conflict is taking place.

CONCLUSION

The dynamics of social conflict represent an objective characteristic of the social system, serving as a source of its self-development and reflecting the evolution of conflict under the influence of internal and external factors. A conceptual analysis of approaches, typologies, and definitions shows that modern social conflict is a complex phenomenon that requires comprehensive knowledge tools. In this regard, the primary task of the researcher is the management of social conflicts. For the development of the basic principles of social conflict management, the following methods can be applied: retrospective analysis of conflict situations, the participant observation method, case studies, and mathematical modeling of social processes using computer technology.

The methodological problems that arise in the study of real social conflicts will be further investigated in order to develop a systematic approach that synthesizes the possibilities of structural-functional, system-situational, and applied analyses of social conflict.

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2025. №9

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